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STATE RESPONSIBILITY AND COMMERCIAL SATELLITE SYSTEMS IN ARMED CONFLICT

KAITLYN THOMAS¹

ABSTRACT

The militarization of outer space is increasingly driven by military reliance on commercial space infrastructure. Privately owned and operated satellite systems are able to provide critical communications, navigation, and intelligence capabilities that have become essential to modern military operations on Earth. These systems are typically inherently dual-use, designed for civilian purposes but easily adaptable to military use. International space law, however, remains rooted in outdated assumptions regarding State ownership and control, raising questions about its capacity to regulate this evolving form of militarization.

This paper examines why existing international frameworks struggle to address military reliance on privately owned satellite systems, using SpaceX's Starlink involvement during the Russia-Ukraine war as an illustrative case. Starlink's rapid integration into Ukraine's military operations highlights a growing disconnect between operational realities and legal applications. This analysis argues that this disconnect reflects a mismatch between traditional State-centric responsibility foundational to international law and the privatized nature of today's space activities.

This paper first examines the evolution of modern militarization, from traditional weapons-based conceptions to the rise of infrastructural militarization through commercial satellite systems. It then assesses the limitations of existing legal regimes, demonstrating their reactive nature and inability to constrain militarization *ex ante*. It then turns to State responsibility, primarily under Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty, arguing that while this offers the most appropriate mechanism for addressing private actor involvement, it remains underdeveloped.

Ultimately, this paper identifies a responsibility gap in which conduct shaping the militarization of outer space is legally recognizable yet effectively unregulated. It concludes that without clearer articulation and enforcement of State responsibility, the normalization of military dependence on commercial satellite systems will continue to outpace the law governing outer space activities.

KEYWORDS: State Responsibility, Militarization of Outer Space, Dual-use Satellite, Article VI.

¹ SCF intern, kaitlyn.thomas@spacecourtfoundation.org

1. INTRODUCTION: COMMERCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND THE QUIET MILITARIZATION OF OUTER SPACE

The militarization of outer space has traditionally been understood through the lens of the deployment of weapons and the conduct of active warfare beyond Earth's atmosphere. International space law, notably the *1967 Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (OST, Outer Space Treaty), reflects this focus by expressly prohibiting nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in outer space.² However, modern military practice increasingly relies on outer space in ways that do not fit this traditional conception. States have increasingly integrated space infrastructure, typically via satellites, into Earth-based military operations. This shift has occurred in parallel with the explosion of commercial activity in outer space, leading to a divergence between law and practice.

Privately operated satellites have become essential to modern military effectiveness. Commercial constellations provide secure communications, intelligence, and navigation assistance at a scale and speed not currently found with many State-owned systems. The capabilities of such satellites are inherently dual-use, as they are designed for civilian purposes but can be readily adapted to military operations. As a result, military integration of commercial space infrastructure has become normalized, even in light of current legal frameworks governing outer space, primarily centered on State-owned and controlled operations with clearly distinguished civilian and military boundaries.

The Russia-Ukraine war is a particularly salient illustration of this transformation. SpaceX's Starlink constellation, a broadband internet service intended for civilian use, was rapidly integrated into Ukraine's military operations, enabling communication among airborne devices and sustaining operations during blackouts. This integration occurred without any formal transfer of ownership or incorporation into Ukraine's military. A private corporation made all decisions related to Ukraine's access to Starlink. Starlink's role exposes a growing discrepancy between how space systems are used in armed conflict and how international law addresses responsibility and regulation.

This paper asserts that existing international space law frameworks are ill-equipped to regulate military reliance on privately owned dual-use satellite systems. It argues that the illustration of Starlink in the Russia-Ukraine conflict reveals a fundamental mismatch between the State-centric responsibility framework found in the current body of space law and the realities of modern militarization in outer space. This mismatch allows the militarization of space without meaningful legal constraint.

The analysis proceeds in six parts. It will first examine the concept of militarization and how it has evolved in outer space in light of the explosion of private intervention. Next, it will present Starlink as a case study of modern militarization. The following section will study Article VI of the OST as a foundational principle for regulating the space activities of non-governmental

² Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, January 17, 1967, Article IV. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/space/space-law/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

entities. Fourth, the analysis will examine other sources of international law (namely, the Liability Convention and IHL principles) to demonstrate why these regimes, while important to armed conflict, are not best suited to address militarization. Finally, it will return to the concept of State responsibility and explain how these frameworks create a responsibility gap, thereby making militarization legally permissible yet largely unregulated.

2. MILITARIZATION OF OUTER SPACE BEYOND WEAPONS SYSTEMS

2.1. *The Evolution of Modern Conceptions of Militarization*

A traditional view of militarization in outer space has largely centered on the deployment of weapons, anti-satellite (ASAT) capabilities, and the potential for kinetic conflict beyond Earth's atmosphere. The potential weaponization of outer space was a salient concern during negotiations of the OST, prompting the drafters to explicitly prohibit the placement of nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in orbit, on celestial bodies, or in void space.³ Other forms of traditional militarization were also considered and prohibited, including the establishment of military bases on the Moon and other celestial bodies.⁴ Additionally, the moon and other celestial bodies were designated exclusively for peaceful purposes rather than for military objectives.

While militarization through non-weaponized means has existed since the beginning of the Cold War, a clearer distinction has since been drawn between weaponization and militarization. Militarization has come to be known as “force enhancement including communications, navigational and intelligence gathering activity”.⁵ Weaponization, by contrast, involves the “proliferation, testing, deployment and use of weapons or counterspace capabilities located in or directed towards space or space systems.”⁶ While the OST addresses specific forms of weaponization, it is less clear regarding the placement of conventional weapons and the military uses of space. This ambiguity has brought about concerns that non-weaponized military space objects could easily be repurposed as weapons or become legitimate military targets during armed conflict.⁷

Militarization in outer space has been an international concern since before space launches became possible. At the height of the Cold War, as the US and Russia developed rocket and nuclear technologies in the early 1950s, they regarded these two technologies as working hand in hand to deliver missiles effectively into the heart of the enemy's territory.⁸ After the launch of Sputnik 1 in 1957, the US accelerated its development program and launched its first military-use surveillance satellite, Discoverer XIII, in 1960.⁹ As the concern of nuclear weapons

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. (2003). *Outer space and global security*. Page 3. United Nations. <https://unidir.org/files/publication/pdfs/outer-space-and-global-security-307.pdf>.

⁶ Space Security Lexicon. (n.d.). *Weaponization of Outer Space*. <https://spacesecuritylexicon.org/terminology/weaponization-of-outer-space>.

⁷ See, for example Farooqui, MO., Qureshi, T. (2024). *Outer space militarization and the emerging paradigm of weaponization: Implications for space security and international regulation*. Rev. Just. Rireito. Hein Online.

⁸ Sheposh, R. (2025). *Militarization of space*. EBSCO Knowledge Advantage. <https://www.ebsco.com/research-starters/military-history-and-science/militarization-space>.

⁹ Ibid.

in space rose throughout the 1960s, the international community came together to pass the Outer Space Treaty in 1967, effectively outlawing nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in outer space. While this treaty serves as the baseline for peaceful conduct in space, it does not expressly prohibit the use of conventional weapons or the militarization of satellites. Spacefaring and non-spacefaring nations alike have used satellites and other objects for military purposes such as surveillance and intelligence sharing. While militarization in outer space is unlikely to cease, it has evolved over the decades to reflect the current realities of space activities.

2.2. Militarization Through Dual-Use Satellites

Modern militarization is increasingly embodied in the integration of space infrastructure into military systems on Earth. Infrastructure becomes militarized through its function and integration into military systems, rather than through its physical design. Dual-use satellites, in particular, enable military effectiveness while remaining non-destructive in nature. In times of armed conflict, militarized infrastructure in the form of connectivity to satellites can act as a force multiplier.¹⁰ Secure communications enable distanced command and control, coordination of geographically dispersed units, and intelligence sharing, among many other capabilities. In the same vein, disruption of these services can significantly impair military effectiveness. As a result, modern militaries around the world have become increasingly reliant on uninterrupted access to reliable satellite communications.

2.3. The Role of Private Actors in Modern Militarization

The explosion of commercial activity in outer space has significantly contributed to this shift in how militarization is constituted today. Private actors now are the main providers of services that were once the exclusive domain of States, such as satellite communications, observation, and positioning. While satellites such as these are designed primarily for civilian purposes, they are inherently dual-use. Dual-use objects can be defined as an “item [which] has civilian applications and military, terrorism, weapons of mass destruction, or law-enforcement-related applications.”¹¹ Current dual-use satellites provide the infrastructure that can serve as weapons platforms and assist with cyber operations, without being weapons themselves.¹² For example, the Finnish company ICEYE owns the world’s largest synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite constellation.¹³ The images created by these satellites are high-resolution and capable of seeing through clouds, smoke, and at night. These satellites were originally endorsed as being used for detecting rapid changes on Earth’s surface, such as flood monitoring and tracking oil spills.¹⁴ Since the first launches of ICEYE’s satellites, they have been used for military purposes by several States’

¹⁰ Aberle, A. (2003). *Strategic force multiplier: The importance of space in the Army’s future*. Space Technology. <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA525762.pdf>.

¹¹ Export Control Reform Act, 50 USC § 4801(2). (2018). [https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=\(title:50%20section:4801%20edition:prelim\)](https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=(title:50%20section:4801%20edition:prelim)).

¹² Pražák, J. (2019). *Weaponization of outer space: Double-edged blade of dual-use technology*. [Master’s thesis, Charles University]. <https://dspace.cuni.cz/bitstream/handle/20.500.11956/107927/120331323.pdf?sequence=1>.

¹³ ICEYE. (n.d.). *About us*. <https://www.iceye.com/company>.

¹⁴ European Space Agency. (2021, December 20). *ICEYE, the world’s first SAR new space constellation*. <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/success-story/iceye-the-world-s-first-sar-new-space-constellation>.

militaries, illustrating how civilian systems can be operationally militarized while remaining legally classified as commercial space activities under international space law.¹⁵

Commercial entities have become particularly attractive partners for satellite use during armed conflict due to their scale of operations and rapid deployment capabilities. Partnerships with these private actors are also commercially beneficial for government entities, as services are generally provided through various channels, including commercial contracts and informal agreements. From a governmental perspective, reliance on commercial providers can reduce costs and accelerate access to advanced technologies. For these private corporations, such partnerships offer significant commercial benefits and market security.

Despite the mutual benefits to governments and private actors of using dual-use technologies for military purposes, this increasing reliance complicates regulatory assumptions at the heart of space law and the law of armed conflict. At the time of the drafting and negotiation of the OST, States were the primary actors in outer space, a fact reflected in these frameworks in the allocation of responsibility and the enforcement of compliance. The integration of commercial infrastructure into military operations blurs the distinction between civilian and military spheres, raising questions about neutrality and responsibility attribution. Commercial satellites that support one State's military operations may be perceived as targets by another State, thereby increasing the risk to civilians and other States. These blurring challenges the core principles of international space law and underscores the growing inadequacy of existing frameworks to address contemporary militarization in outer space.

3. STARLINK AND THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR AS AN ILLUSTRATIVE CASE

Armed conflicts of recent decades have underscored the growing significance of military reliance on commercially operated space systems. Among the most prominent and recent examples is SpaceX's Starlink usage during the Russia-Ukraine war. Starlink operates in low-Earth orbit to deliver low-latency broadband internet worldwide.¹⁶ According to Starlink's web page on the satellite technology of the constellation, the internet capabilities support "streaming, online gaming, video calls and more."¹⁷ While "more" is likely to be interpreted in a broad sense, streaming, online gaming, and video calls are primarily used in civilian contexts.

3.1. Starlink's Contributions to the Russia-Ukraine Conflict

Starlink had been pivotal for Ukraine in the earlier days of the conflict with Russia. On February 26, 2022, just two days after the start of the war, Ukraine's Minister of Digital Transformation asked SpaceX CEO Elon Musk via X to provide the country with Starlink services to provide stable communication for its civilians and government.¹⁸ On the same day, Musk tweeted that

¹⁵ ICEYE. (2025, September 10). *ICEYE launches the ISR Cell, bringing tactical space-based intelligence anywhere* [Press release]. <https://www.iceye.com/newsroom/press-releases/iceye-launches-the-isr-cell-bringing-tactical-space-based-intelligence-anywhere>.

¹⁶ Starlink. (n.d.). <https://starlink.com/>.

¹⁷ Technology. (n.d.). <https://starlink.com/technology>.

¹⁸ Fedorov, M. [@fedorovmykhailo]. (2022, February 26). @elonmusk, while you try to colonize Mars – Russia try to occupy Ukraine! [Post]. X. <https://x.com/FedorovMykhailo/status/1497543633293266944?s=20>.

Starlink services were now active in Ukraine with terminals en route.¹⁹ Two days later, 500 ground terminals arrived in Ukraine.²⁰ Ukrainian citizens were thus able to stay connected to friends and family online. Additionally, energy companies and hospitals were able to remain open and operational, providing essential services to Ukrainians.²¹

Not only did the Ukrainian civilian populace benefit substantially from Starlink's rapid integration, but the Ukrainian military also stood to gain significantly from these new capabilities. Troops used Starlink for reconnaissance, coordination of counterattacks, artillery fire direction, and drone-strike operations.²² The use of Starlink involved no transfer of ownership or formal incorporation into Ukraine's armed forces. Rather, a privately owned satellite system was integrated into military operations while remaining under SpaceX's commercial control. The resulting arrangement illustrates how dual-use space technologies can become central to military operations without formal legal incorporation into State-owned armed forces.

3.2. Legal Problems Arising from Starlink's Involvement in the War

Despite the rapid deployment of Starlink in Ukraine's military operations, this integration raises several complications for classifying the satellites. Although the satellites were neither designed nor registered for military purposes, their operational role in supporting Ukraine's armed forces challenges the assumption that classification depends solely on design or intent. This blurring is particularly significant in space, where satellite systems are increasingly difficult to distinguish between civilian and military uses. As a result, existing legal frameworks struggle to account for such systems, whose status may fluctuate based on function rather than classification.

This difficulty in classification, particularly for systems owned by private actors, is significant because it raises questions about the applicability of various international law frameworks. For instance, in the context of traditional terrestrial armed conflict, several treaties exist regarding international humanitarian law, targeting, responsibility, liability for damages, and neutrality. However, when private actors enter the scene, the application of international law becomes significantly ambiguous, and these actors can evade its application.

In the context of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, authorization was granted for Starlink to be deployed in Ukraine, but similar access was not permitted in Russia.²³ This gave a significant military advantage to Ukraine. Similarly, in September 2022, it was reportedly decided that Starlink's connection in Ukraine would be disrupted during a counteroffensive against Russian

¹⁹ Musk, E. [@elonmusk]. (2022, February 26). *Starlink service is now active in Ukraine. More terminals en route.* [Post]. X. <https://x.com/elonmusk/status/1497701484003213317>.

²⁰ Abels, J. (2024). Private infrastructure in geopolitical conflicts: The case of Starlink and the war in Ukraine. *European Journal of International Relations*, 30(4), 853. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540661241260653>.

²¹ Press, L. (2026, January 6). *Starlink in Ukraine: What three years of wartime connectivity taught us.* CircleID. <https://circleid.com/posts/starlink-in-ukraine-what-three-years-of-wartime-connectivity-taught-us>.

²² Private infrastructure in geopolitical conflicts, 853.

²³ Smith, E. (2024, February 12). *Musk denies selling Starlink terminals to Russia after Kyiv alleges their use in occupied areas.* CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/2024/02/12/musk-denies-selling-starlink-terminals-to-russia-after-kyiv-alleges-use.html>.

forces, resulting in the mission's failure.²⁴ This selective treatment by a private corporation, rather than by State command structures, during armed conflict raises numerous questions about how Starlink interacts with international humanitarian law, whether Starlink satellites could be legitimate targets of Russian counterstrikes, and whether Starlink or SpaceX could be held responsible or liable for damages.

3.3. *Starlink as an Illustration, not a Precedent*

Starlink's involvement in the Russia-Ukraine war is not unique when considering the role of private entities operating in space during armed conflict. The Gulf War in the 1990s is widely regarded as the first international conflict to rely heavily on commercially operated space-based infrastructure.²⁵ Reliance on private corporations' satellite systems has only increased during times of armed conflict.

The legal binds illustrated by Starlink's role in the Russia-Ukraine war bring to the fore a central challenge for international space law: when military operations are conducted through commercial systems beyond direct State ownership or control, determining who bears responsibility, and on what basis, becomes profoundly uncertain. This incoherence between operational reliance and legal attribution sets the stage for examining whether existing doctrines of State responsibility can meaningfully address the militarization of commercial space systems.

4. STATE RESPONSIBILITY UNDER INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW

4.1. *Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty*

Responsibility is not only a foundational concept in international space law; its application in outer space entails a novel consideration in international law: the role of private actors. Article VI of the OST explicitly sets out obligations relating to "non-governmental entities," which undoubtedly includes private actors. Article VI states:

States Parties to the Treaty shall bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, whether such activities are carried on by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities, and for assuring that national activities are carried out in conformity with the provisions set forth in the present Treaty. The activities of non-governmental entities in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, shall require authorization and continuing supervision by the appropriate State Party to the Treaty. When activities are carried on in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, by an international organization, responsibility for compliance with this Treaty shall be borne both by the international organization and by the States Parties to the Treaty participating in such organization.²⁶

²⁴ Roulette, J., Bryan-Low, C., and T. Balmforth. (2025, July 25). *Musk ordered shutdown of Starlink satellite service as Ukraine retook territory from Russia.* Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/investigations/musk-ordered-shutdown-starlink-satellite-service-ukraine-retook-territory-ru-ssia-2025-07-25/>.

²⁵ Tepper, E. (2022). The first space-cyber war and the new for new regimes and policies. *Center for International Governance Innovation*, 173, 2. https://www.cigionline.org/static/documents/PB_no.173_uPqYILM.pdf.

²⁶ Outer Space Treaty. Article VI.

This article provides the basis for international responsibility in outer-space contexts, particularly for private entities. Since non-governmental entities lack legal standing under international space law, this article places the onus on the State to ensure that all activities undertaken by such entities comply with the provisions of the OST. Furthermore, the second sentence of Article VI imposes obligations on States to authorize and continuously supervise the activities of non-governmental entities, thereby ensuring that State responsibility is maintained throughout the activity's life cycle.

Under Article VI, the first criterion for its application is a State's violation of an obligation, rather than the occurrence of damage, either by failing to authorize national activities or by failing to maintain continuous supervision of the entity carrying out the activity. Secondly, attribution to a State must be established. Attribution under Article VI does not require operational control over each activity but instead emanates from the characterization of activities as “national” from both governmental and non-governmental actors. The OST does not define “national activities,” but rather only specifies that they are the activities of “governmental agencies” or “non-governmental entities.” This broad formulation deliberately avoids a control-based designation, instead extending responsibility to all activities attributable to a State’s governmental or non-governmental entities, thereby capturing private commercial operations within the scope of international responsibility.

4.2. States’ Obligations Posed by Article VI

Article VI imposes three obligations on State parties regarding the national activities of non-governmental entities. First, States must “assure” that national activities are carried out in conformity with the provisions set forth in the treaty.²⁷ The word “assure” implies that States must be certain that national activities comply with international law.²⁸ The OST does not provide specific instructions on how to achieve this assurance, but it is generally understood that this entails States regulating national activities and exercising due diligence to prevent harm to others.

The second obligation requires States to authorize national activities. As is common with terms in the OST, the treaty does not define “authorization,” nor does it specify how authorization is ensured. However, it is largely interpreted and implemented through domestic licensing requirements.²⁹ National agencies such as the US Federal Communications Commission (the FCC) and *France’s Centre National d’Études Spatiales* regulate this authorization, ensuring State compliance with the OST.

Finally, States must continually supervise national activities. This obligation is twofold. Firstly, the supervision must be constant throughout the life of the space activity. The second aspect is more open to interpretation. Again, silent on its definition, the OST does not specify what “supervision” entails, thereby leaving a large margin of appreciation to States. Using the FCC as an example, the agency maintains oversight of space activities by setting reporting requirements

²⁷ Outer Space Treaty. Article VI.

²⁸ *What obligations does the OST Article VI impose on states?* (n.d.). Marius. <https://www.sjorettsfondet.no/journal/2024/584/m-1776>.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

for space station operators and by requiring annual lists identifying satellites providing services.³⁰

4.3. State Responsibility in the Militarization Context

When considering the broader context of militarization in outer space, it is important to note that State responsibility persists regardless of military utility. It has been established that militarization is not inherently illegal under the provisions of the OST. Thus, responsibility can be triggered even when the use is lawful. Moreover, Article VI does not preclude the application of State responsibility for any reason, including the use of satellites owned by private operators during periods of armed conflict. The operation of such satellites would still fall under the definition of “national activities” carried out by a “non-governmental entity,” consequently compelling States to respect their obligations.

While Article IV of the OST provides the foundational principle for State responsibility regarding non-governmental space activities, it is not the only provision regulating potential or realized harms. Other frameworks of international law also attempt to regulate damages and conduct arising during armed conflict. However, these regimes rely on distinct and sometimes narrow assumptions that limit their effectiveness in addressing militarization through privately operated satellite systems.

5. THE LIMITS OF LIABILITY AND OTHER LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN ADDRESSING MILITARIZATION THROUGH SATELLITES OPERATED BY PRIVATE ACTORS

5.1. The Liability Convention

Outer space is governed by its own liability regime enshrined in the *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects of 1972* (Liability Convention). It should be noted here that while in certain languages, such as French and Spanish, the term “responsibility” encompasses what is in English responsibility and liability. Therefore, a distinction must be made. Responsibility is engaged for internationally wrongful acts and breaches of international obligations. Liability, on the other hand, refers to acts that are not illegal but nonetheless cause damage to others.

The Liability Convention provides a system for determining liability that is rather unique to international law. Traditionally, liability is determined by control. For example, Article 106 of the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea* (UNCLOS) states that in cases of maritime seizures, the “State making the seizure shall be liable to the State the nationality of which is possessed by the ship or aircraft for any loss or damage caused by the seizure.”³¹ However, the Liability Convention’s focus on ownership rather than control has created a regime that

³⁰ Applications for earth station authorizations, 42 CFR § 25.115, 1997. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-47/chapter-I/subchapter-B/part-25/subpart-B/subject-group-ECFR2bd70fc6b2eea0/section-25.115> and Space station point of contact reporting requirements, 47 CFR § 25.171, 2023. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-47/chapter-I/subchapter-B/part-25#25.117>.

³¹ United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, December 10, 1982, Article 106. https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

inaccurately reflects contemporary realities and may impose liability on States with no direct involvement in conflicts.

The Liability Convention operates under a dual-liability regime. The first pillar of liability is absolute liability, which concerns damage on the surface of the earth or to aircraft.³² The sole exception to this determination is found in Article VI, which exonerates a launching state from liability in cases of gross negligence or intentional damage-causing omissions done by a claimant State or its natural or juridical persons.³³

The second pillar centers on fault-based liability, which is enshrined in Article III, stating:

In the event of damage being caused elsewhere than on the surface of the earth to a space object of one launching State or to persons or property on board such a space object by a space object of another launching State, the latter shall be liable only if the damage is due to its fault or the fault of persons for whom it is responsible.³⁴

Several nuances must be considered here. Firstly, fault-based liability is attributed only if the damage is caused at a location other than the Earth's surface, thereby meaning on a celestial body, in Earth's orbit, or in void space. Additionally, the damage must occur to a space object or to persons or property on board a space object.

5.2. The Liability Convention's Difficulties in Addressing Militarization

Liability is ill-suited to address the questions that arise from Starlink's involvement in the Russia-Ukraine conflict and broader militarization. First, the definition of "damage" does not encompass the types of harm that may be caused by the use of satellites for military purposes. Article I of the Liability Convention defines "damage" as "loss of life, personal injury or other impairment of health; or loss of or damage to property of States or of persons, natural or juridical, or property of international intergovernmental organizations."³⁵ While definitions in international law can be extremely useful, this narrow definition does not address emerging forms of damage that have become crucial in the context of space activities, as it is limited to physical damage. It does not consider other types of indirect losses, such as environmental damage, economic losses, or, in the case of the Russia-Ukraine war, strategic losses.

Additionally, liability attribution further complicates matters when considering the given definition of "launching State." Per Article I of the Liability Convention, a launching State is either the "State which launches or procures the launching of a space object" or the "State from whose territory or facility a space object is launched."³⁶ In light of the Starlink illustration, the United States would be determined as the launching State in both senses of the definition, as the satellites are launched from the US. Following this reasoning, the US could be held liable for any

³² Conventino on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, March 29, 1972, Article II. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

³³ Liability Convention, Article II.

³⁴ Liability Convention, Article III.

³⁵ Liability Convention, Article I.

³⁶ Ibid.

damages that Ukraine inflicted upon Russia during the war, even though the US had no direct affiliation with the hostilities.

In the broader context of broader space militarization, the Liability Convention remains less effective than proactive measures to prevent damage caused by dual-use objects through State responsibility. Since the Liability Convention requires that harm have occurred for it to apply, liability is imposed too late and does little to prevent it. Moreover, compensation as provided for by the Convention does not deter States or private corporations from lawful military integration. Even where liability could theoretically be attributed, the Convention operates only after harm has occurred, offering no mechanism to constrain the integration of commercial systems into military operations *ex ante*.

5.3. Applications of International Humanitarian Law

Despite the apparent failures of the Liability Convention in the context of militarization through privately owned dual-use objects, adjacent international law applicable to armed conflict still poses complications. The application of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) provisions to outer-space operations during armed conflict has been the subject of debate for decades. This analysis rests on the assumption that the current body of IHL is sufficiently applicable to outer space, though it presents complications when attributing responsibility for privately operated dual-use satellites. IHL is ill-suited to regulate the normalization of military dependence on space infrastructure precisely because it presumes an act of violence rather than persistent infrastructural integration. Returning to the problem of classification, dual-use objects pose a central challenge. Under IHL provisions, civilian objects are protected under IHL that sit under the umbrella of the principle of distinction.³⁷ This principle obliges parties to a conflict to distinguish at all times between military and civilian objects and between combatants and civilians, and to direct operations only against military objectives.³⁸ However, when those objects are used for military purposes, they lose that protection.³⁹ The question of dual-use satellites and their protection under IHL becomes problematic because these space objects are inherently designed to serve both commercial and military purposes, even if military purposes are not their primary objective.

The principle of proportionality is also important here. This principle prohibits attacks that would cause disproportionate harm to civilians relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁴⁰ Proportionality works in corollary with the principle of distinction as it recognizes that incidental harm to civilians and civilian objects is unavoidable during armed conflict. Thus, it places a limit on the extent to which this harm is permissible.⁴¹ An attack on a dual-use satellite would likely cause significant communication disruptions, including loss of GPS navigation or even general internet access, over large geographic areas. Additionally, this principle would only apply once

³⁷ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949 and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), June 8, 1977, Article 52. https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/external/doc/en/assets/files/other/icrc_002_0321.pdf.

³⁸ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949, Article 48.

³⁹ ICRC. (n.d.). Rule 10. Civilian objects' loss of protection from attack. *International Humanitarian Law Databases*. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/customary-ihl/v1/rule10>.

⁴⁰ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949. Article 57.

⁴¹ Berrang, S. (202, November 2). How would IHL apply to hostilities in outer space? *Humanitarian Law & Policy*. <https://blogs.icrc.org/law-and-policy/2023/11/02/how-would-ihl-apply-to-hostilities-in-outer-space/>.

an attack has manifested. However, militarization by dual-use satellites resists this application as it merely enables operations and shapes potential outcomes.

Further underscoring the inadequacy of existing international law, the fragmentation of these regimes just studied demonstrates their systemic failure to constrain the militarization of outer space. The Liability Convention lays the groundwork for compensatory measures for ex post damages, provided that certain conditions are met. IHL provisions are similarly reactive and specific to active armed conflicts, rather than to the incremental normalization of military dependence that often occurs outside these conflicts.

In light of this analysis, the limitations of these regimes highlight the need to shift the analytical focus toward State responsibility, which, although less enforceable, offers a broader framework for examining State obligations regarding privately operated space systems used in armed conflicts.

6. THE RESPONSIBILITY GAP

6.1. State Responsibility as a Better Suited Regime to Address Militarization

While liability and IHL principles respond to harm after it occurs or depend on narrow classifications, State responsibility, as outlined in Article VI of the OST, offers a broader, conduct-based regime that is better suited to addressing militarization through commercial space systems. However, the current responsibility framework remains underdeveloped and ambiguously applied, further failing to address militarization.

Despite the evident failures of adjacent international law, State responsibility remains a better framework for addressing concerns about militarization. Firstly, responsibility relies on the conduct of States. In contrast, the Liability Convention, for example, requires physical damage to have occurred to apply. In the context of Article VI of the OST, responsibility mirrors the applications found in general international law. It arises in cases involving violations of relevant legal obligations or wrongful acts, regardless of whether physical harm occurs.⁴² This differs greatly from liability, as it concerns only compensation for damages arising from acts that are not illegal.

Thus, responsibility is able to be engaged earlier, specifically before harm occurs. Under Article VI of the OST, responsibility is triggered by a State's failure to authorize or continuously supervise activities of non-governmental entities. In the context of Starlink and its integration into Ukraine's military forces, State responsibility could be applied more readily than liability or other IHL provisions. For instance, the US would be the State responsible for Starlink, as SpaceX is an American non-governmental entity. If the US were found to have failed to effectively authorize or supervise SpaceX's activities, one could argue that it had breached its obligations under Article VI of the OST, even before any damage would have occurred.

⁴² Von der Dunk, F. (1991). Liability versus responsibility in space law: Misconception or misconstruction? *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program Faculty Publications*, 43, 366. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1042&context=spacelaw>.

However, as the following paragraphs explain, State responsibility remains an inadequate framework for addressing militarization through dual-use satellites.

6.2. Shortcomings of Reliance on State Responsibility

One of the main issues undermining responsibility, particularly in the Starlink context, is attribution. General international law and the ILC's Draft Articles on State Responsibility for Internationally Wrongful Acts have been adopted and implemented by States over the decades, resulting in a clear regime of attribution for traditional tools used in armed conflict, even those owned by private enterprises.⁴³ In outer space, however, this attribution is significantly more difficult, particularly for dual-use systems. Considering the Starlink illustration, attribution becomes uncertain where operational decisions affecting military outcomes are made by a private operator rather than State instruction. In applications of general international law in which State control is the determining factor for attribution, private entities are excluded. Since Starlink was not formally transferred to Ukraine and remained under private control, responsibility would be nearly impossible to determine. Even with respect to Article VI of the OST, responsibility attribution challenges persist. Although responsibility is assigned to States for national activities, it does not offer guidance on when it should be applied when day-to-day operational decisions are exercised through private entities for military purposes.

Responsibility is also difficult to apply to militarization because it is not inherently illegal. Article VI requires States to ensure that non-governmental entities comply with the OST's provisions, including that space is used for the benefit and interest of all countries and is the province of all mankind. It is commonly understood that conducting peaceful activities in outer space does not exclude military applications for non-hostile purposes.⁴⁴ Dual-use satellites such as Starlink exemplify this difficulty. Even when used by Ukraine's armed forces for military purposes, Starlink satellites were not employed for aggressive or hostile activities in outer space; they merely facilitated terrestrial military operations. Thus, provided that the US authorized and supervised Starlink's operations, it could be argued that no obligation had been violated either by SpaceX or the US.

Furthermore, responsibility is additionally weak in addressing militarization due to the lack of enforcement mechanisms. On an international scale, enforcement can be difficult to achieve, especially if no mechanism exists in the violated legal framework. Generally, in public international law, enforcement centers on the cessation of the wrongful act and three forms of reparation (restitution, compensation, and satisfaction).⁴⁵ Otherwise, international enforcement is typically carried out through diplomatic means, where an injured State may bring claims against the injuring State or through countermeasures under certain constraints.⁴⁶

⁴³ Von der Dunk, F. (2024, July 26). Space privateers or space pirates? Armed conflict, outer space, and the attribution of no-state activities. *Articles of War*. <https://lieber.westpoint.edu/space-privateers-pirates-outer-space-attribution-non-state-activities/>.

⁴⁴ See for example, National Aeronautics and Space Council. (1959, December 17). NSC 5918/1. US policy on outer space. *Dwight D. Eisenhower Presidential Library and Museum*. <https://aerospace.csis.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/NSC-5918-US-Policy-on-Outer-Space.pdf>.

⁴⁵ Draft Articles on Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts, May 31, 2001, Articles 30-31 and 34-37. https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/draft_articles/9_6_2001.pdf.

⁴⁶ Draft Articles on Responsibility of States, Articles 48-49.

The shortcomings in State responsibility reveal a gap between the legal design of international space law and the realities of contemporary military practice. As commercial actors increasingly provide the infrastructure upon which military effectiveness depends, the absence of clear regulatory constraints enables militarization to expand through privatized systems with limited accountability. The concluding section reflects on the broader implications of this mismatch and considers how the evolving role of commercial space infrastructure challenges the foundational assumptions of international space law.

7. CONCLUSION

The increasing integration of commercial space infrastructure into military operations marks a shift in the militarization of outer space. Unlike earlier forms of militarization centered on weapons deployment or military installations, modern militarization relies on infrastructure and is often indistinguishable from civilian use. Privately operated dual-use satellite systems now serve as enablers of military forces, reshaping strategic realities on Earth while remaining formally classified as civilian space activities under international law.

This study has shown that the current legal frameworks do little to address the growing normalization of militarization through dual-use systems owned by corporate entities. The Liability Convention offers a narrow, damage-based regime that applies only *ex post* and fails to consider the types of strategic harm generally connected to military reliance on commercial satellites. International humanitarian law, while essential during active hostilities, is similarly reactive and ill-equipped to regulate the normalization of military dependence on space infrastructure. Its reliance on object classification and armed conflict operations leaves significant gaps when applied to dual-use systems operating beyond traditional conceptions of warfare.

Considering this context, State responsibility under Article VI of the OST arises as the most conceptually appropriate framework for addressing militarization through privately operated space systems. Unlike liability regimes, responsibility focuses on State conduct and can be engaged regardless of physical damage. It imposes obligations on States to authorize and continuously supervise the space activities of non-governmental entities, offering a foundation for addressing military integration *ex ante*. However, this framework remains underdeveloped and ambiguously applied. Difficulties of attribution, the permissibility of militarization under the OST, and the absence of enforcement mechanisms undermine its effectiveness.

These shortcomings result in a responsibility gap in which States can externalize military functions to commercial actors to evade effective legal accountability. Starlink should therefore be understood not as an exceptional case, but as a cautionary tale. As commercial space actors continue to expand their role in global connectivity and security, the mismatch between legal principles and operational reality will only deepen. Without clearer articulation and enforcement of State responsibility, the militarization of outer space through commercial infrastructure risks becoming normalized and legally unchecked, thus reshaping the strategic environment in ways international space law is currently not designed to address.